

Teachers' Perspective on Low-Income Family Engagement to Teacher-Parent Partnership

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Abstract. The study found that low-income families encounter challenges that hinder their academic involvement. The target population for this study was the twelve (12) participants from the line-up of elementary faculty who are still teaching during the first semester of the school year 2022-2023. The study's result disclosed that teacher-parent partnerships play a significant role in helping low-income families overcome the barriers to academic involvement. When teachers actively establish connections with parents, it fosters open lines of communication and creates an inclusive environment. Teachers' perspective of family low-income learners related to teacher-parent partnership, barriers to academic involvement among low-income families building trust and rapport with low-income families resources and support for teachers working with low-income families challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families, strategies that teachers use to engage low-income, families in their child's academic progress the importance of effective communication educational outcomes of effective teacher-parent partnerships incorporating the perspectives and input of low-income families policies and practices to promote educational equity for low-income families. Further, to discuss the results in the future, we should explore and implement more flexible assessment models that align with student-centered practices. This may require a shift away from traditional exams and a focus on alternative ways of evaluating student progress.

KEY WORDS

1. Teacher perspective
2. family low-income learners
3. teacher-parent partnership

1. Introduction

Nurturing low-income families has been a priority on the Philippine agenda. More and more parents face the difficult task of raising their children alone. More children than at any time live in poverty today in the Philippines. The achievement gap between low-income and high-income pupils has been well documented in the literature, with children in poverty having more academic and behavioral problems. Aside from providing knowledge and the necessary values and skills children need to develop intellectually, education is generally perceived as a human and social capital, parents desire what they perceive is best for their children, and across social and cultural groups, there is a consensus in the literature that parents have high regard for their children's education. In the global context. Academic involvement in children's education is a vital component in young children's motivation and academic achievement. Furthermore, academic involvement contributes to children's school readiness (Hill, 2021), read-

ing proficiency, math, and vocabulary skills (El Nokali, Bachman, Votruba-Drzal, 2021). When parents are involved, they may gain information on how and what to teach their children. Involved parents also provide their children with opportunities to practice and further develop what they have learned in school. Academic involvement conveys to children that parents are interested and invested in their development (Hango, 2019), and this possibly provides children with motivation to do well in school. Lastly, parents participating in school send a message to their children that school is important (Fan, Williams, Wolters, 2019) and children imbibe this value and become more positive about learning. Given that academic involvement benefits children in numerous ways, it has become the subject of educational research and policy for years (Gordon Cui, Moroni, Dumont, Trautwein, Niggli, Baeriswyl, 2019). In the national context, the achievement gap between low-income and high-income pupils has been well documented in the literature, with children in poverty having more academic and behavioral problems, and higher school dropout rates. Although there are numerous factors that contribute to this disparity (e.g., disproportionate access to high-quality schools and other resources), academic involvement may play a role in bridging the gap in children's school outcomes (LaRocque, Kleiman, Darling, 2021). However, notwithstanding the benefits of academic involvement, various factors facilitate and hinder involvement, with some barriers identified as beyond parental control, such as access to technology and other socio-cultural factors. Families in poverty are especially vulnerable to factors that can hinder academic involvement; for instance, the economic pressure and financial stresses can constrain their capacities to involve themselves in their children's schooling (Conger Donnellan, 2019). Although there is an abundance of studies that examine academic involvement, current research offers a limited understanding of academic involvement in non-Western countries, especially in Asian countries, most likely the developing ones. For instance, mainstream measures of academic involvement do not include paying for school tuition fees when in some countries (e.g. Bangladesh, Indonesia) this is the chief indicator that parents care about their children's education (Kabir Akter, Karsidi, Humona, Budiati, Wardoyo, 2019). In the local context, this poses validity issues as parents are measured against standards which may not be reflective of their experiences and cultural beliefs. As such, it is important to employ a cultural lens and start with an exploratory study to build a model that can help understand and examine academic involvement among the target population (Yoder Lopez, 2020). The researcher has taught for many years in Pilar Elementary School, in Monkayo East, Division of Davao de Oro. She has been in close contact with low-income Filipino families. Their priority lies in responding to the basic needs of the family; hence, parental, and familial involvement is relegated to the background. Their involvement is only a few days in Brigada and oftentimes, forced attendance is exchanged with daily livelihood. The researcher focused her study on this kind of family in public school education.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this study was to present teachers' perspicacity of family incomes related to definitions and dimensions of teacher-parent partnership. The Philippines is a developing country with high rates of poverty and education deficits. School dropout rates are also high especially among children and youth from disadvantaged backgrounds (Albert, Dumagan, Martinez, 2019). Knowing the significance of academic involvement, this study explored the concept of academic involvement among low-income Filipino parents and its

1.2. *Research Questions*—This study is guided by the research questions:

- (1) What is the lived experience of teachers that may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to teacher-parent partnership?
- (2) How do teachers cope with the challenges that hinders academic involvement among low-income families?
- (3) What educational insights can be derived from the findings of the study?

1.3. *Review of Related Literature*—Family Incomes The traditional Filipino family emphasizes strong cohesion, respect for elders, and the value of education. Fathers typically act as protectors and primary financial providers, while mothers are the primary caregivers and manage children's education (Alampay Jocson, 2019). Education is viewed as an investment for the family, with children often valuing it to fulfill familial obligations (Reyes Galang, 2019).

Barriers to Academic Involvement Among Low-Income Families Research indicates that family involvement positively impacts student motivation (Reyes Galang, 2019). However, low-income families often face barriers such as lack of personal interest in school, high education costs, and insufficient support (PIDS, 2019; Tabbada-Rungduin et al., 2019). Poor education quality and limited resources further hinder the academic involvement of children from these backgrounds (Yap, 2011).

Building Trust and Rapport with Low-Income Families Parent-teacher partnerships are essential for positively influencing children's educational outcomes. Hoover-Dempsey et al. (2020) propose that parental motivation, invitations to involvement, and parents' life contexts significantly impact academic involvement. Effective partnerships require understanding the complex interplay of these factors (Eccles Harold, 2019).

Resources and Support for Teachers Working with Low-Income Families Household income is a crucial predictor of academic involvement, with higher-income families providing more support (Lopez, 2019). Social and cultural capital, parents' educational levels, and

psychological resources also influence involvement (Grenfell James, 2019; Clarke, 2021). Mothers tend to be more involved than fathers across different cultures (Sheng, 2019; Kabir Akter, 2020).

Challenges Faced by Teachers Working with Low-Income Families Increased stress due to poverty negatively affects academic involvement. Parents experiencing stress or depression are less likely to be involved (Hornby Lafaele, 2021; Baeck, 2020). Children's academic performance can drive parental involvement, with struggling students needing more support (Shumow Miller, 2021).

Strategies for Engaging Low-Income Families in Academic Progress Schools play a critical role in fostering academic involvement. Effective communication and specialized programs can enhance parental engagement (Epstein, 2021; Castillo Gamez, 2019). However, teachers' heavy workloads and negative attitudes towards low-income families can hinder these efforts (Arcangel, 2019; Sukhbaatar, 2019).

The Importance of Effective Communication Cultural context significantly influences academic involvement. In collectivistic cultures like the Philippines, parental roles in education are often seen as distinct from those of teachers (Denessen et al., 2001; Sy, 2019). Understanding these cultural influences is crucial for promoting academic involvement.

Educational Outcomes of Effective Teacher-Parent Partnerships Government policies and programs can enhance academic involvement. Effective teacher-parent partnerships improve children's academic performance, motivation,

and overall well-being (Crosby et al., 2019; Wilder, 2018; Gonzalez-DeHass et al., 2020). Despite the lack of specific policies in the Philip-

1.4. Theoretical Lens—Nurturing low-income families has been a priority on the Philippine agenda. More and more parents face the difficult task of raising their children alone. More children than at any time live in poverty today in the Philippines. The achievement gap between low-income and high-income pupils has been well documented in the literature, with children in poverty having more academic and behavioral problems. Aside from providing knowledge and the necessary values and skills children need to develop intellectually, education is generally perceived as a human and social capital, parents desire what they perceive is best for their children, and across social and cultural groups, there is a consensus in the literature that parents have high regard for their children’s education. In the global context. Academic involvement in children’s education is a vital component in young children’s motivation and academic achievement. Furthermore, academic involvement contributes to children’s school readiness (Hill, 2021), reading proficiency, math, and vocabulary skills (El Nokali, Bachman, Votruba-Drzal, 2021). When parents are involved, they may gain information on how and what to teach their children. Involved parents also provide their children with opportunities to practice and further develop what they have learned in school. Academic involvement conveys to children that parents are interested and invested in their development (Hango, 2019), and this possibly provides children with motivation to do well in school. Lastly, parents participating in school send a message to their children that school is important (Fan, Williams, Wolters, 2019) and children imbibe this value and become more positive about learning. Given that academic involvement benefits children in numerous ways, it has become the subject of educational research and policy for years (Gordon Cui, Moroni, Dumont, Trautwein, Niggli, Baeriswyl, 2019). In the national context, the achievement gap between low-income and high-income pupils has been well documented in the literature, with children in poverty having more academic and behavioral problems, and higher school dropout rates. Although there are numerous factors that contribute to this disparity (e.g., disproportionate access to high-quality schools and other resources), academic involvement may play a role in bridging the gap in children’s school outcomes (LaRocque, Kleiman, Darling, 2021). However, notwithstanding the benefits of academic involvement, various factors facilitate and hinder involvement, with some barriers identified as beyond parental control, such as access to technology and other socio-cultural factors. Families in poverty are especially vulnerable to factors that can hinder academic involvement; for instance, the economic pressure and financial stresses can constrain their capacities to involve themselves in their children’s schooling (Conger Donnellan, 2019). Although there is an abundance of studies that examine academic involvement, current research offers a limited understanding of academic involvement in non-Western countries, especially in Asian countries, most likely the developing ones. For instance, mainstream measures of academic involvement do not include paying for school tuition fees when in some countries (e.g. Bangladesh, Indonesia) this is the chief indicator that parents care about their children’s education (Kabir Akter, Karsidi, Humona, Budiati, Wardojo, 2019). In the local context, this poses validity issues as parents are measured against standards which

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

may not be reflective of their experiences and cultural beliefs. As such, it is important to employ a cultural lens and start with an exploratory study to build a model that can help understand and examine academic involvement among the target population (Yoder Lopez, 2020). The researcher has taught for many years in Pilar Elementary School, in Monkayo East, Division of Davao de Oro. She has been in close con-

tact with low-income Filipino families. Their priority lies in responding to the basic needs of the family; hence, parental, and familial involvement is relegated to the background. Their involvement is only a few days in Brigada and oftentimes, forced attendance is exchanged with daily livelihood. The researcher focused her study on this kind of family in public school education.

Figure 1 shows the theoretical/conceptual framework of the study was to present teachers' perspicacity of family incomes related to definitions and dimensions of teacher-parent partnership. Knowing the significance of academic involvement, this study explored the concept of academic involvement among low-income Filipino parents and its role in children's educational outcomes. The purposes of this study are to explore culturally embedded and indigenous meanings of academic involvement in schooling; to identify factors that facilitate or hinder academic involvement among low-income families; and c) to gather the insights of the parents on academic involvement to improve students' academic performance. In that sense, the schematic analysis of the study rooted from the following questions: What is perspicacity of teachers towards family incomes related to definitions and dimensions of teacher-parent partnership? How do family incomes hinder the academic involvement among low-income families, and the last one is educational insights can be derived from the findings of the study To

make the study more comprehensive to the readers and beneficiaries the following terms will be defined based on the objectives or purpose of the study. teachers' perspective of family low-incomes learners related to teacher-parent partnership, in this study teachers' perspective of family low-incomes. In this study refers to they can play a critical role in establishing a positive and effective partnership with parents. By recognizing the unique challenges that low-income families face, teachers can work to create a supportive and inclusive classroom environment that promotes academic success and fosters positive relationships with parents related to teacher-parent partnership. Teachers' perspective. This study refers to the teachers' perception of family low incomes can have an impact on their ability to establish effective partnerships with parents. When teachers are aware of the challenges that low-income families face, they are better equipped to provide appropriate support and establish a positive relationship with parents. Family Low-Incomes. In this study refers to the financial constraints

that some families face and may be more empathetic and flexible when it comes to issues such as school fees or the cost of supplies. Additionally, teachers who recognize that low-income families may have limited access to resources like books, technology, or transportation, may be more proactive in providing these resources or finding alternative solutions. Teacher-Parent Partnership. In this study refers to the collaborative relationship between teachers and parents/guardians that supports the academic, social, and emotional development of students. This partnership is critical to ensure that students receive the necessary support both at school and at home to succeed academically and socially. An effective Teacher-Parent Partnership is essential to ensure that students receive the necessary support to succeed academically and socially. By working collaboratively, teachers and parents can create a supportive and inclusive learning environment that promotes academic success and fosters positive relationships between the school and families. The study is significant because of the benefits to the following: Department of Education (DeEd). Low-income parents have less contact with schools than do their better-off counterparts. The department of education is now aware that family income is a factor and there is a need for support. Ele-

mentary School. Schools need to establish clear school and district policies on family involvement and reach out to all parents on a continuing basis, providing personal contact, literature and classes on parenting, literacy training, and parental resource centers. Teachers. Many children are left at home alone, unsupervised or watching television for hours a day. Working parents are often faced with trying to complete all household duties in the limited time available. Teachers also are strapped for time. Although some would like to make home visits to families or talk more with students' parents, many teachers are parents themselves and have families to attend to. Parents. The plight of children of low-income families can find better education in the hands of a caring and compassionate government. Community. Religious and civic organizations need to encourage parents as they guide the growth of their children. Communities also must work with families to make the streets safe for children and provide constructive after-school and summer experiences. Respectful and Inclusive Environment: Teachers can create a respectful and inclusive classroom environment that welcomes parents from diverse backgrounds and values their contributions to their child's education.

2. Method

This chapter, the researcher introduced the philosophical assumptions, qualitative assumptions, research participants, data collections, data analysis, ethical considerations, role of the researcher, and trustworthiness.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—It was assumed that all participants answered interview questions honestly and to the best of their abilities. It was further assumed that the sample used for this study was representative of in-depth and focus group interviews on a face-to-face manner as a medium of communication. These assumptions have been articulated throughout

the last 20 years in the various SAGE Handbooks of Qualitative Research (Denzin Lincoln, 1994, 2000, 2005, 2011) and as the “axiomatic” issues advanced by Guba and Lincoln (1988) as the guiding philosophy behind qualitative research. These beliefs have been called paradigms (Lincoln, 1985), philosophical assumptions, epistemologies, and ontolo-

gies (Crotty, 1998), broadly conceived research methodologies (Neuman, 2000), and alternative knowledge claims (Creswell, 2014). There were beliefs about ontology (the nature of reality), epistemology (what counts as knowledge and how knowledge claims are justified), axiology (the role of values in research), and methodology (the process of research). In this discussion, I would first discuss each of these philosophical assumptions, detail how they might be used and written into qualitative research, and then link them to different interpretive frameworks that operate at a more specific level in the research process.

Ontology. The issue relates to the nature of reality and its characteristics; when researchers conduct qualitative research, they embrace the idea of the unfolding of the story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to the personality development of pupils. Different researchers embrace different realities, as do the individuals being studied and the readers of a qualitative study. When studying individuals, qualitative researchers conduct a study with the intent of reporting these multiple realities. Evidence of multiple realities includes the use of various forms of evidence in themes using the actual words of different individuals and presenting different perspectives. For example, when writers compile a phenomenology, they report how individuals participating in the study view their experiences differently (Moustakas, 1994).

Epistemology. Conducting a qualitative study means the researcher tries to get as close as possible to the study participants. Therefore, subjective evidence is assembled based on individual views. The very reason why I chose these elementary teachers as my participants is because I have known them for quite a long time. This is how knowledge is known through the subjective experiences of people. It becomes essential, then, to conduct studies in the “field” where the participants live and work; these are important contexts for understanding what the participants are saying. The longer a researcher

stays in the “field” or get to know the participants, the more they “know what they know” from firsthand information. For example, good phenomenology requires a prolonged stay at the research site (Wolcott, 2008). In short, the researcher tries to minimize the “distance” or “objective separateness” (Guba Lincoln, 1988) between himself or herself and those being researched.

Axiology. This assumption characterizes qualitative research. How does the researcher implement this assumption in practice? In a qualitative study, the inquirers admit the study’s value-laden nature and actively report their values and biases as well as the value-laden nature of information gathered from the field. This means that the result of this study will be shared with the school where I am currently working. We say that they “position themselves” in a study. In an interpretive biography, for example, the researcher’s presence is apparent in the text, and the author admits that the stories voiced represent an interpretation and presentation of the author as much as the subject of the study (Denzin, 1989). I believe that I am more qualified to conduct this study since I have ample experience teaching in elementary.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions of the Study—The researcher made these qualitative assumptions that consist of the methods used in the process of qualitative research (Creswell 2003). The procedures used by the researcher are inductive and are based on the researcher’s own experience in collecting and analyzing data. The research here is the product of the values of the researcher. Through an inductive approach, raw textual data is condensed into a brief, summary format. Clear links are established between research objectives and summary findings derived from raw data. A framework of the underlying structure of experiences or processes that are evident from the raw data is developed. A phenomenological study describes the meaning of lived experiences of individuals about a concept or phenomenon

(Creswell, 2003) was used in this study. A phenomenological study intends to understand and describe an event from the point of view of the participants. A key characteristic of this approach is to study how members of a group or community interpret themselves, the world, and life around them (Mertens, 2005). The purpose of this study was to explore how mathematics teachers in first through fifth grade were using effective instructional practices, related to building background, student interactions, and application, to meet the needs of EL students as well as the possible challenges experienced by teachers when implementing these practices. Collectively, these results may provide foundational information to guide the district in addressing the local issue. Administrators might benefit from this information as it might enable them to make informed decisions about what support is needed for teachers' perspicacity of family incomes related to definitions and dimensions of teacher-parent partnership. In addition, this study was to discover the teachers' perspicacity of family incomes related to definitions and dimensions of teacher-parent partnership. in selected elementary schools appear to have experienced towards teachers' perspicacity of family incomes related to definitions and dimensions of teacher-parent partnership, specifically in the areas of building background knowledge, interactions, and application.

2.3. Design and Procedure—In the next section, the specific details of the research procedures were described so future researchers can generalize the results from this study to other situations. Extensive and careful descriptions of the time, place, context, and culture of the study will be thoroughly discussed to develop transferability, which is the qualitative parallel to external validity in post-positivist research (Mertens, 2005). This section will discuss the interview approach, explain the role of the researcher, and lastly, describe the sampling method and ethical considerations.

Semi-Structured Interviews. Patton (2015) proposes researchers conduct interviews to learn the things they cannot directly observe. Qualitative interviewing is not used to get answers to questions but to understand the experiences of the participants and the meaning they make of that experience (Seidman, 1988). Generally, qualitative studies use unstructured, open-ended interviews because they allow for the most flexibility and responsiveness to emerging issues for both the participants and interviewer; however, the use of semi-structured interviews is not uncommon and used when the researcher seeks to obtain specific, more focused information (Schwandt, 2001). Semi-structured interviews combine the flexibility of unstructured, open-ended interviews with directionality and an agenda to produce focused, qualitative, textual data (Schensul, LeCompte, (1999). This study collected data using semi-structured interviews to explore teachers' perspicacity of family incomes related to definitions and dimensions of teacher-parent partnership. An interview guide was used to ensure that the same information was collected from all the participants. The interview guide included open-ended questions and topics to help structure the interview. Still, when needed, the interviewer also explored, probed, and asked additional questions to clarify and expand on a particular topic. The interview guide helped make interviewing several participants more systematic and comprehensive by defining the issues to be explored (Patton, 2015). The open-ended questions were framed to allow the participants to represent their views and perspectives in their own words and terms and take the questions in any direction that they chose (Patton, 2015). Since qualitative research studies subjects in their natural setting, all interviews except one took place using a face-to-face format at a time convenient for the participants. All interview sessions were tape-recorded for transcription. When needed, the researcher used follow-up interviews after

transcription to clarify meaning or explore areas in more depth.

2.4. Research Participants—The target population for this study was the twelve (12) participants from the line-up of elementary faculty who are still teaching during the school year 2022-2023. This study utilized an in-depth interview. The researcher considered the faculty from selected public schools who are still teaching. A sample of twelve (12) elementary school teachers was chosen purposefully from this population. As a researcher, I used purposive sampling (also known as judgment, selective, or subjective sampling), a sampling technique in which the researcher relies on their judgment when choosing population members to participate in the study. This survey sampling method requires researchers to know the purpose of their studies in order to choose and approach eligible participants properly (Denzin, 2017). The participants of this study were elementary teachers from the selected public schools in the Monkayo East district and supervisors of Davao De Oro. Below was a simple description of the participants: Participant 1 was a licensed professional teacher and lives in Monkayo East district supervisor of Davao De Oro. She has been an experienced teacher for almost 3 years, and she/he taught general education subjects among elementary pupils.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical standards were required in conducting research; thus, this phenomenological research adheres to the essential elements and principles of the Belmont Report (1979), which strictly observed the principles of respect of persons, beneficence, and justice. Specifically, this study was subjected to the evaluation of the the college where the researcher is studying for the full board review of the ethical aspects of the investigation as regards the dimensions of research ethics that include social value, informed consent, vulnerability issues, risk-benefit ratio, privacy and confidentiality of information, justice, transparency,

qualification of the researchers, adequacy of facilities and community involvement. Social Value. The researcher investigated and carefully analyzed one of the pressing problems in our educational system. Also, this research concerns the unfolding story of teachers' sleep deprivation and its relationship to pupil personality development. This study is expected to provide important information in recognizing the extent and type of experiences that basic education teachers experience. The findings of this study could provide more insights among basic education teachers and students to maintain quality teaching and learning. The researcher is hopeful that the study's output is relevant not only to the participants but also to the school. The study's results would be presented in local, national, and even international fora and, if given a chance, published in an international publication. Informed consent. In this study, informed consent was secured from all the participants who were involved. The researcher conducted a detailed and comprehensive explanation regarding the purpose of the survey of twelve (12) basic education teachers. The researcher ensured that the condition of the consent was a voluntary choice. The participants had sufficient information and an adequate understanding of both the proposal and the implications of their participation in the study. Codes were assigned to individuals in the data presented. Every page of the transcriptions of the in-depth interview and focus group discussions was signed by the researcher to attest that the key informant interviews were done with the consent of informants. In addition, the informants were accorded the needed respect. The researcher made it a point that the form must bear the signature of the participant or agreement, which would imply that she participated in the study voluntarily. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The researcher protected the participants from being deceived, threatened, and forced to participate. The researcher treated them with the highest respect.

Thus, they were informed ahead of time that they might withdraw their participation in the study, and if any inconvenience was felt during the interview and in answering the questionnaire, they would be given a chance to raise their concern and opt to cancel the activity. Although the participants were of legal age, 18 years old and above, they were still vulnerable because the researcher is an elementary teacher in Monkayo East district supervisor of Davao De Oro, one of the selected research locales of the study. Teachers were treated with utmost respect so they would not be vulnerable while participating in this study. I considered the basic education teachers participants in this study because they were mature enough to decide whether to participate. Risks-Benefit Safety. A careful assessment of foreseeable risks, burdens, and benefits to the participants was made. My questionnaire did not contain degrading, discriminating, or unacceptable language that was offensive to the participants, so the risks were avoided. An extra careful approach was used in collecting the data so that irrelevant and confidential details were rejected. The study did not involve any high-risk situation that the participants may experience in their social and emotional needs. Further, this study ensured that the potential benefits of the participants were greater than the potential harm. The results of this study would benefit the entire department of education, teachers, students, parents, and the community, in terms of getting a clear rationalization to synthesize various activities that would address the teacher's insight of family incomes related to definitions and dimensions of teacher-parent partnership. Practically, the researcher identified only minimal risks, if not negligible, regarding physical harm or discomfort that they may experience during the conduct of the study. Specifically, whatever might adversely affect the respondents' personal relationships, loss of status, privacy, or time was taken into consideration in the planning stage of the study so that such effects would be minimized if not prevented fully. The mild inconvenience was a possible minimal risk that the researcher had identified that respondents may experience due to their busy schedule brought about by the varying tasks in school and at home. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. The current study ensured the privacy and confidentiality of the respondents' information. The researcher adhered to the principles of the Data Privacy Act of 2012, or Republic Act 10173, which mandates transparency, legitimate purpose, and proportionality in the collection, retention, and processing of personal information (Congress of the Philippines, 2012). This act protected the fundamentals of human rights on the privacy of information, ensuring the free flow of information that promotes innovation and growth. The researcher protected the respondent/participants' right to privacy wherein their responses were given with the highest respect. Unless required by the law, the confidentiality of information shall always be observed. Other personal information would not be asked in the study to safeguard their identities and enable them to participate without fearing the revelation of involvement in the study. Any information would be taken with utmost care to ensure the anonymity of the data sources and de-identify any personal information that would be shared. Such names and identities were protected by using a pseudonym. Tracing these codes' information was reflected in an archival log. Hence, personal names were not used to trace the identification. Written responses, if any, were captured through a camera. Recordings were saved, and documents were kept in one place, protected or encrypted. Justice. In this study, justice requires an equitable distribution of both the burdens and the benefits of participation in research. There was a fair selection in the choice of population, sampling, and assignments. Provision of appropriate care to research participants regardless of their eco-

conomic status, gender, race, or creed was provided. With this, the researcher assured the respondents who were involved were appropriate for the study. I provided just compensation and reimbursement for data used and costs incurred by the participants. The participants were adequately informed on the study's objectives before they were involved in the process. It was emphasized that they were the source of data and encouraged to give their honest answers in the survey questionnaire. In return, they were the priority for the benefits of the possible offshoots of the study findings. Transparency. To be ethical, all the parties need to be transparent by ensuring that the process, the nature of the study, and the extent of participation are clear and understandable to the participants. The researcher tried to get the willingness of the participants to participate in the study and ensured that they could withdraw their participation if necessary. The researcher was transparent about the aspects of the study, especially the information that has a bearing on the decision of participants to give or withhold their informed consent. The participants can access and scrutinize the study's findings if the findings were scientifically valid and have significant implications on the participant's well-being. The researcher assured us that the study was conveyed in full scope and accurately. Specifically, in qualitative data analysis, findings were identified, confirmed, or rejected accordingly. Moreover, data transcriptions were presented to the participants to attain precision. Consequently, the researcher ensured the reasonable availability and accessibility of the research outcomes to the Department of Education, teachers, students, parents, and the community. Qualification of the Researcher. I am ultimately responsible and accountable for the research. For the research to be carried out with the necessary skills and knowledge. I am aware of the limits of personal competence in research. With my experience as an elementary teacher in one of the pub-

lic schools in Monkayo East district supervisor of Davao De Oro. I attended several research-related seminars and training which I consider as an asset in conducting this study with the assistance of my adviser and colleagues, readings from various books and literature, fulfilling my duties and responsibilities at RMC as an elementary teacher and the supervision of RMC-REC, I acquired the knowledge and skills needed to conduct the research. Also, the supervision and direction of his adviser and the panelists helped improve the research study. The researcher's adviser is an expert in this study. Therefore, the adviser is a big help to complete the study with the quality of the content. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher is adequately equipped with the budget and equipment to conduct the study. This ensured that the researcher had the best facilities to complete the research. The researcher personally owns the laptop, printer, internet connection, and other necessary facilities, making them adequately and readily available. Furthermore, non-online and online library resources such as books, ProQuest, OECD, EBSCO, and Google are readily available. In addition, if possible, Google Meet was used to gather the data. Aside from the enumerated resources, some experts provided the researcher with the guidance needed in the conduct of this research like the adviser, RMC-Research Ethics Committee, and panel members who are also the expert validators. Community Involvement. The researcher is engaged with communities like the Public Schools academic community, teachers, parents, and the basic education students since I am a teacher in one of the public schools in Monkayo East district supervisor of Davao De Oro is composed of quite diverse people; thus, the researcher is sensitive to and respects the cultural, traditional, and religious practices of the community. The RMC graduate school helped correct, validate, and revise the manuscript for the current study. The RMC graduate school provided directions to the re-

researcher based on its research standards and practices. The elementary teachers, students, and parents participated in the development of the questionnaire through the output of the first phase of the study. The guide questions served as the instrument in gathering qualitative data in the second phase. On the other hand, proper protocol and seeking approval from the principal of the public schools as my target participants were observed. Moreover, the significant personas in the public-school organizational landscape and other stakeholders may benefit from the output of the study because they are the recipients of the data regarding knowledge about the instructional practices for education. Further, the result would be presented to the stakeholders including the elementary education community and the output will serve as an aid for policy development to address the issues concerning the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development of pupils. Data Collection

2.6. *Data Collection*—Prior to the data gathering, I must ask for the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of the college where the researcher is studying to pursue the study. After the permissions were approved by the school division superintendent and the school principals of the target participants, I talked to the participants to acquaint them with the purpose of the study. I agree with the participants on the most convenient date and time for the interview. To start the interview, I asked the participants to read the respondents' consent forms and affix their signatures on the consent papers after they had been oriented to the study's purpose and had agreed to the terms and conditions. I emphasized to the respondents that they are allowed to ask questions to clarify any matter regarding the study and ask their consent to record the conversation with the assurance that everything shall be dealt with utmost confidentiality. Through the in-depth interviews, I gathered the teachers' feelings, reac-

tions, observations, and experiences regarding the teachers' perspicacity of family low incomes related to the teacher-parent partnership. The interviews also included gathering information about obstacles and challenges that the teachers encounter with the home visitations. I will likewise aim to obtain substantial information on teachers' perspicacity of family low-incomes related to teacher-parent partnership that helps bridge the risk of understanding and making together to identify and address academic and non-academic needs of students. This could involve setting academic goals, monitoring progress, and providing support at home. According to Koontz and Weinrich (2000), the process and narratives do not need to be transcribed verbatim if the essence of the participants' communication has been caught in the transcription. Individual transcriptions of the interview were validated by the respective participants. To verify and revalidate the data gathered, I conduct focus group discussions to validate and triangulate the information gathered. Corrections may be made according to the participants' feedback to ensure that the meaning was conveyed in the fundamental structure of the phenomenon. Data from interviews, field notes, and recorded videos were collected through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. Field notes recorded nonverbal communication and participants' interactions with the environment. The questionnaire was a combination of closed and open-ended questions administered by the researcher orally. Interviews were semi-structured, employed open-ended questions, and were based on an interview guide. Data were generated through field notes, a voice recorder, or cell-phone videos during participant interviews. A piloted interview questionnaire was used with all participants. Twelve participants were interviewed in two sessions of 45 minutes to 60 minutes each because of their schedules. The interval between interviews was, on average, one day. Interview questions were based on the

study's four research questions, which explored participants' viewpoints. Follow-up questions were also made to clarify ambiguous comments and discrepant data. In four instances, participants preferred to discuss the ambiguities over high-quality attributes. In a qualitative phenomenological study, research data involved the researcher spending as much time as possible with the teachers at the elementary schools to gain an in-depth understanding of the elementary teachers in their everyday lives. Participant observations of the elementary faculty behaviors, beliefs, traditions, culture, and social and emotional interactions were recorded at the end of each day in a journal. Where applicable, in-depth interviews were conducted in field settings, recorded, transcribed, and/or summarized in the journal. As an active participant in the research process, the researcher constantly evaluated her role and her relationship with participants and applied this to develop an understanding and interpretation of the basic education teacher's social and emotional worlds (Unger, 2005). This resulted in an evolving research process, both in terms of the direction and type of data derived and in terms of the researcher's personal transformation (Parker, 2005). The evolution of the research as a relational transformation between a researcher with openness to a new experience and a community of participants cannot be over-emphasized. The results could not have been foreseen at the inception of this study (Parker, 2005). As noted earlier, the location of the study is an academic institution that experienced changes in its way of teaching. The researcher has already spent several years as an elementary teacher, and I have a great chance to gather demographic information and meet as many locals as possible. Also, it was hoped that an initial understanding of the community culture could be gained through participant observation. Effective Teacher-Parent Partnership involves ongoing communication, mutual trust, respect, and a shared commitment to student

success. Some of how teachers can establish effective partnerships with parents include Regular Communication: Teachers can establish regular communication channels with parents to share updates on academic progress, behavior, and social-emotional well-being. This can be done through emails, phone calls, newsletters, or parent-teacher conferences. Active Listening: Teachers could actively listen to parents' concerns and feedback, and work collaboratively to find solutions that support student success. I engaged the junior high teachers' community to meet up with the gatekeeper she worked with. I liaised with the teacher coordinator and interacted with some teachers. Participant observation data was obtained and recorded in a journal, while access to participants for focus groups was limited. All participants signed an informed consent form before being interviewed. I translated questionnaires into the language commonly used by the participants. Data collection was multimodal. According to Yin (2003), the main characteristic of phenomenological qualitative research is that it employs various data collection methods to ensure the report's trustworthiness. Multiple data sources promote a clearer understanding of the data being studied (Creswell, 2008, 2009; Glesne, 2011; Merriam, 2009). Interview questions were based on the study's four research questions, which explored participants' viewpoints. Follow-up questions clarified ambiguous comments and discrepant data. In four instances, participants preferred to discuss the ambiguities over high-quality attributes.

2.7. Data Analysis—Qualitative data analysis begins with organizing, reducing, and describing the collected data (Schwandt, 2001). Unlike quantitative analysis, there are no prescribed formulas for qualitative analysis. Marshall and Rossman (2006) remind researchers that qualitative analysis does not proceed linearly and is not neat. However, good practice and procedures enhance the credibility of qual-

itative research. In this last section, the data analysis procedures were explained, and the steps taken to ensure the results from this study are credible, transferable, dependable, and authentic were thoroughly described. To guide the data analysis, the researcher used the seven phases of data analysis described by Marshall and Rossman (2006) to reduce data, create manageable pieces, allow for interpretation, and find meaning in the words of the participants. The seven phases included organizing the data, immersion in the data, generating categories and themes, coding the data, offering interpretations through analytic memos, and searching for alternative understandings (Marshall Rossman, 2006). Data analysis first begins with organizing the data. The organization of the data involved keeping information provided by each participant separate and in sequence with the order of the interviews. The process of organizing the data allowed it to remain manageable, easily accessible, and readily available. The digital audio files from the interviews were carefully transcribed into written form. Electronic folders were established to organize the data collected from each participant. Next, the researcher became familiar with the data by reading the interviews extensively to understand their content. This involved reading through the interviews at least three times. Following Hatch's (2002) recommendations for qualitative analysis, the researcher created a sheet of notes for each participant. The summary sheets were a quick way to refer to the original data as the data analysis continued (Hatch, 2002). After the initial readings, Hatch (2002) recommends researchers read data through completely with one typology in mind. Patton (2015) defines typologies as classification systems made up of categories that divide some aspects of the world into parts. According to Hatch (2002), typologies are generated from theory, common sense, or research objectives. For this study, the researcher used the typologies or themes from the literature re-

view as the constructs through which to view the data. After reading through the data with each constructor typology in mind, the researcher coded the data into five categories from the literature by taking excerpts of text from the data and identifying it within a particular category. After everything was coded, the researcher read through the data again while writing analytic memos on her thoughts and insights and began offering interpretations. During this stage, the researcher began to interpret the data to find significance and meaning in the teachers' instructional experiences by pulling salient themes, re-occurring ideas, and patterns of belief that resonated collectively throughout the interviews. The offering of interpretations began following the emergence of themes in the data. Marshall and Rossman (2006) believe this part of the data analysis brings meaning to the themes and categories and allows the researcher to develop links between the interviews. The researcher began to interpret the data to find significance and meaning in the unfolding story of teachers towards teacher's perspicacity of family incomes related to definitions and dimensions of teacher-parent partnership. The experiences were analyzed to provide insight and feelings on making a difference in the educational system. Both aim to provide information on the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to the personality development of pupils. The data collected during interviews was transcribed, organized, and reviewed in searching for patterns and themes. Because this study involved human participants, informed consent was secured for ethical purposes. Following signing consent forms, the story of teachers' views on sleep deprivation related to the personality development of pupils is unfolded using semi-structured, in-depth interviews. Data was organized and analyzed. The researcher rigorously examined these units of meaning to elicit the essence of meaning within the holistic context. The entire interview transcript and add

anything that might have been left out. The information may be shared with the participants in a circle to ensure that we interpreted the data correctly using triangulation analysis (Mazuwelics, 2018). Thematic Content Analysis was used to interpret the responses made by the key participants and determine the lessons and insights derived from teachers' perspectives on family incomes related to definitions and dimensions of teacher-parent partnership. Their responses were processed and conducted through analyses. Transcripts were coded in considerable detail with the focus shifting back and forth from the key claims of the participants to the researcher's interpretation of the meaning of the responses and subjectively interpreted. Meanwhile, the notes that may be obtained from in-depth interviews may be transcribed immediately. The researcher may look for common themes among the responses to each question. In this phase, the researcher may use thematic analysis to analyze the gathered data. Their responses were processed and conducted through analysis. Transcripts were coded in detail, with the focus shifting back and forth from the key claims of the participants to the researcher's interpretation of the meaning of the responses and subjectively interpreted. Meanwhile, the notes obtained from in-depth interviews may be transcribed immediately. The researcher may be looking for common themes found among the responses to each question. Environmental Triangulation. Triangulation analysis is a tool developed by Margaret Schuler to help advocates perform a strategic analysis of the issues they are working on. The tool examines three aspects: content, structure, and culture. Triangular analysis is a technique for both analyzing and finding answers to a problem, structured around structure, content, and culture in the policy system, which was done through transcribing, member checking, and triangulation. The entire interview transcript and add anything that might have been left out. The information may

be shared with the participants in a circle to ensure that we interpreted the data correctly using triangulation analysis. The researcher must possess trustworthiness and credibility to achieve a truthful and productive result in a qualitative study. With this, the researcher religiously followed the requirements (Mazuwelics, 2018).

2.8. *Framework of Analysis*—The analytical framework for this study was flexible enough to allow the researcher to either gather all of the data and then analyze it or evaluate it while it was being collected. The data collected was then sifted, charted, and categorized in line with key topics and themes during the analysis stage. This process involves familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization was becoming familiar with the data through reading and re-reading interview transcripts. Familiarizing the whole interview with the audio recording and transcript and any contextual or reflective notes the researcher recorded was a vital stage in interpretation. It could also be helpful to re-listen to all or parts of the audio recording. The researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, exploring the field, or reading transcripts. The researcher would become aware of critical ideas and recurring themes throughout the procedure and would make a note of them. The researcher may be unable to review all of the material due to the enormous amount of data that might be collected in qualitative research. As a result, a portion of the data set would be utilized. Several elements of the data collection method would influence the selection. Coding was the process of summarizing and representing data in order to provide a systematic account of the recorded or observed phenomenon. After familiarization, the researcher carefully reads the transcript line by line, applying a paraphrase or label that is a 'code' that describes what they have interpreted in the passage as necessary. Coding aimed to

classify the data to be compared systematically with other parts of the data set. Developing a thematic framework happens after coding a few transcripts. The researcher needs to compare the labels applied and select a set of codes to apply to all subsequent transcripts. Codes could be grouped into categories, which are then clearly defined. This forms a working analytical framework. Several iterations of the analytical framework were likely required before no additional codes emerged. It was always worth having another code under each category to avoid ignoring data that does not fit; the analytical framework was never ‘final’ until the last transcript had been coded. Indexing involves identifying portions or sections of data that relate to a specific theme. This procedure is conducted using all textual data collected, such as transcripts of interviews. Ritchie and Spencer (1994) suggest using a numerical system to index references and annotating them in the margin beside the text for ease. Qualitative data analysis tools are

ideal for this task. Charting involves summarizing the data by category from each transcript. Good charting requires an ability to strike a balance between reducing the data on the one hand and retaining the original meanings and ‘feel’ of the interviewees’ words on the other. The chart should include references to exciting or illustrative quotations. The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, includes an analysis of the essential qualities depicted in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, assisting the researcher in interpreting the data set. I must be cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis and define concepts, map the range and nature of phenomena, create typologies, find associations, provide explanations, and develop strategies (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994). These concepts, technologies, and associations mirror the participant. Therefore, any strategies or recommendations the researcher offers reflect the participants’ real views, beliefs, and values.

2.9. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Qualitative research does not claim to be replicable. The researcher purposefully avoids controlling the research conditions and concentrates on recording the complexity of situational contexts and interrelations as they occur naturally (Marshall Rossman, 2006). This study took many extra steps to ensure the results from the data analysis were credible, transferable, dependable, and authentic. Credibility. Mertens (2020) defines credibility as a correspondence between the way a participant perceived social constructs and the way the researcher portrays the participant’s viewpoints. To ensure credibility in this study, the researcher used persistent observation that allowed for interviews that were long enough to identify salient issues (Mertens, 2020). The researcher also monitored her developing constructions and documented any changes she experienced from the

beginning of the study to the end in the analytic memos. This procedure began with the researcher’s disclosure of values, beliefs, and experiences that connect her to the topic of research regarding instructional practices for English learners in Elementary Mathematics. Transferability. Establishing transferability provides the degree to which the results can be generalized to other situations. The researcher kept an audit trail, which is a meticulous record of the research process so other researchers can recapture steps and the same conclusions. Extensive and careful descriptions of the time, place, context, and culture of the study were kept developing a thick description (Mertens, 2020). Conformability. “Conformability means that the data and the interpretation are not figments of the researcher’s imagination” (Mertens, 2005, p. 257). In this study, the data gathered will be analyzed and interpreted properly to arrive

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

at a convincing theme that would further discuss the importance of teacher’s perspicacity of family incomes related to definitions and dimensions of teacher-parent partnership. To establish conformability, the researcher kept track of the qualitative data so it can be tracked to its source in the interviews. Authenticity. To establish authenticity within the study, the researcher

presents a balanced view of all perspectives, values, and beliefs. As a researcher, I must avoid bias in gathering the data. This study used peer debriefing to play the role is asking tough questions about the data collection, data analysis, and data interpretations (Newton Rudestam, 2001).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the results of the data analysis and the discussion of the results of the study, which focused on teachers’ perspectives of family low-income learners related to teacher-parent partnership was gathered to specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: What is the lived experience of teachers that may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to teacher-parent partnership. How do teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families? What educational insights can be derived from the findings of the study? Before I begin my discussion, I would like to establish the symbols I used as I present the quotations based on the responses of the participants of the study. In reference to the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, I used codes to refer to participants of the research question. Their responses were contained and bounded around the three (3) research questions of the study. Moreover, the responses of participants were transcribed in a verbatim manner, translated into English, encoded, and summarized in matrix form, which led to

a schema. The first objective of this study is the lived experience of teachers that may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to teacher-parent partnership. The study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, having three major themes, barriers to academic involvement among low-income families, building trust and rapport with low-income families, and lastly, resources and support for teachers working with low-income families. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers' perspective of family low-income learners related to teacher-parent partnership emerged with the theme, of barriers to academic involvement among low-income families, building trust and rapport with low-income families, resources, and support for teachers working with low-income families.

3.1. Teachers lived experience of teachers that may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to teacher-parent —

*3.1.1. Barriers to Academic involvement among low-income families—*As an educator, it is crucial to reflect on the challenges and barriers faced by low-income families when it comes to academic involvement. Our recent research explored this issue and also delved into the vital aspect of teacher-parent partnerships in addressing these barriers. This reflection highlights key insights from our findings and how they impact our approach to teaching and engaging with the families of low-income learners. As I analyzed from the narration of the study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, having three major themes, barriers to academic involvement among low-income families, building trust and rapport with low-income families, and lastly, resources and support for teachers working with low-income families. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers' perspective of family low-income learners related to teacher-parent partnership emerged with the theme, of barriers to academic involvement among low-income families, building trust and rapport with low-income families, resources and support for teachers working with low-income families. Exploring the Teachers' perspective of family low-income learners related to teacher-parent partnership merged with the first theme of barriers to academic involvement among low-income families. Another local preliminary study, using univariate analyses,

found that Filipino parents always remind their children of the importance of going to school the same study also found that parents believe that they are their children's first teacher, especially in learning how to read. Given that children from disadvantaged backgrounds do not get enough support (PIDS, 2019) and many parents are not equipped with skills to support their children's education, (Tabbada-Rungduin, Abulon, Fetalvero, Suatengco, 2019). As I analyzed from the teachers' perspective of family low-income learners related to teacher-parent partnership learning is becoming increasingly important in the workforce, where collaboration, problem-solving, and critical thinking are highly valued. The lived experience of teachers may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to the teacher-parent partnership. From the perspective of teachers, a strong teacher-parent partnership is essential to monitor and improve a student's academic progress. They view collaboration as a powerful tool in overcoming the barriers faced by low-income families. As I analyzed from the teachers' perspective of family low-income learners related to teacher-parent partnership learning is becoming increasingly important in the workforce, these sample responses offer an idea of how teachers might address the challenges faced by low-income families and the importance of building effective teacher-parent partnerships in the context of these obstacles. Actual responses from teachers in a research study would provide more specific and nuanced insights. This

literature review examines the These sample responses offer an idea of how teachers might address the challenges faced by low-income families and the importance of building effective teacher-parent partnerships in the context of these obstacles. Actual responses from teachers in a research study would provide more specific and nuanced insights. They are making efforts to incorporate more student-centered elements into their teaching, indicating a gradual shift towards adapting their pedagogy, the first objective of this study is the lived experiences of teachers' perspective of family low-income learners related to teacher-parent partnership Reyes and Galang (2019) also maintained that parents and family contribute positively to students' motivation in school. An extensive search of the literature, as well as direct communication with several prominent Filipino scholars in the Philippines and other Southeast Asian countries, resulted in finding only one published empirical study focusing on academic involvement among Filipinos, findings revealed that middle- and high-income Filipino parents scored high in involvement with homework and in volunteering (Blair, 2019). On the other hand, the first objective of this study is the lived experience of teachers that may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to teacher-parent partnership.

3.1.2. Building trust and rapport with low-income families—Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers' perspective of family low-income learners related to teacher-parent partnership emerged with the theme, of building trust and rapport with low-income families, resources, and support for teachers working with low-income families. Exploring the Teachers' perspective of family low-income learners related to teacher-parent partnership merged with the first theme of barriers to academic involvement among low-income families, Building trust and rapport with low-income families. As I analyzed the narration from the reflec-

tion highlights key insights from our findings and how they impact our approach to teaching and engaging with the families of low-income learners. These barriers range from financial constraints to limited access to educational resources and a lack of time due to multiple jobs. It is evident that these challenges significantly affect a family's ability to be fully engaged in their child's academic journey. The first is parental motivation which includes role construction and efficacy beliefs. Role construction includes the parent's perception of responsibility regarding the child's schooling and efficacy refers to the belief that personal actions will effectively help the child. The second element is invitations to involvement from the school, teacher, and student. Invitations from these three sources are important as they suggest that actively participating in the child's schooling is welcome and valued. The third element pertains to the parents' life contexts such as socioeconomic status and parent's knowledge and skills, and how these resources, or lack of them, influence practices related to their children's education. The succeeding sections discuss these elements in more detail (Eccles Harold, 2019). As I analyzed the narration this teacher has a positive outlook and is open One of the most striking observations from our study is the realization that many low-income families desperately want to be involved in their child's education. They value education and understand its importance, yet their circumstances often prevent them from doing so effectively. This As I analyzed the narration from the reflection highlights key insights from our findings and how they impact our approach to teaching and engaging with the families of low-income learners. As I analyzed the narration this teacher has a positive outlook and is open One of the most striking observations from our study is the realization that many low-income families desperately want to be involved in their child's education. They value education and understand

its importance, yet their circumstances often prevent them from doing so effectively. This As I analyzed the narration from the reflection highlights key insights from our findings and how they impact our approach to teaching and engaging with the families of low-income learners. As I analyzed the narration this teacher has a positive outlook and is open One of the most striking observations from our study is the realization that many low-income families desperately want to be involved in their child's education. They value education and understand its importance, yet their circumstances often prevent them from doing so effectively. This As I analyzed the narration from the reflection highlights key insights from our findings and how they impact our approach to teaching and engaging with the families of low-income learners. On the other hand, the first objective of this study is the lived experience of teachers that may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to teacher-parent partnership.

3.1.3. Resources and support for teachers working with low-income families. —As I analyzed the narration this teacher has a positive outlook and is open One of the most striking observations from our study is the realization that many low-income families desperately want to be involved in their child's education. They value education and understand its importance, yet their circumstances often prevent them from doing so effectively. This As I analyzed the narration from the reflection highlights key insights from our findings and how they impact our approach to teaching and engaging with the families of low-income learners. Societal factors such as demographic and economic characteristics are implicated in the nature and extent of academic involvement First, household income is an important predictor of academic involvement, with children from high-income families receiving greater parental support. This is a consistent finding in all the studies that accounted for income Lopez, 2019). As I analyzed

the narration this teacher has a positive outlook and is open One of the most striking observations from our study is the realization that many low-income families desperately want to be involved in their child's education. They value education and understand its importance, yet their circumstances often prevent them from doing so effectively. This As I analyzed the narration from the reflection highlights key insights from our findings and how they impact our approach to teaching and engaging with the families of low-income learners. As I analyzed the narration this teacher has a positive outlook and is open One of the most striking observations from our study is the realization that many low-income families desperately want to be involved in their child's education. They value education and understand its importance, yet their circumstances often prevent them from doing so effectively. This As I analyzed the narration from the reflection highlights key insights from our findings and how they impact our approach to teaching and engaging with the families of low-income learners. As I analyzed the narration this teacher has a positive outlook and is open One of the most striking observations from our study is the realization that many low-income families desperately want to be involved in their child's education. They value education and understand its importance, yet their circumstances often prevent them from doing so effectively. The low-income and working-class context also implies that parents are not able to provide resources that could enhance their children's learning. On the other hand, better-off families have more time and access to information that helps them in assisting their children in school. Research has also noted, however, that professional, busy working parents also reported not having enough time to communicate with their children's teachers (Clarke, Kabir Akter, Lau et al.;,hare Kerrins, 2020). In connection to parent's educational background, as academic lessons become more demanding as stu-

Fig. 3. Thematic Framework of the lived experience of teachers that may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to teacher-parent partnership

dents move up in grade level, parents may not have the necessary skills to assist their children academically (Trumbull et al., 2019). It is also plausible, however, that academic involvement does not actually decrease but only evolves to

subtle forms of parental support such as engaging children in conversations which still support literacy (Hartas, 2017; Kaplan Toren Seginer, 2019).

3.2. *Teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families*—The second objective of this study is the teachers do teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families, considering the three major themes as Challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families, Strategies that teachers use to engage low-income families in their child’s academic progress, and the importance of effective communication. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers do teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families, considering the three major themes as challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families, Strategies that teachers use to engage low-income families in their child’s academic progress, and the importance of effective communication. Therefore, based on the research questions the study dealt with this study is the

teachers do teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families, considering the major theme as reflection emphasizes the importance of teacher-parent partnerships in helping low-income families overcome barriers to academic involvement and underscores the role of teachers in facilitating these partnerships for the benefit of their students.

3.2.1. *Challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families*—I analyzed the narration of challenges in challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families. Based on the research questions that the study dealt with, the reflection can be adapted to directly address those questions. Here’s a response that specifically focuses on how teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families while emphasizing the importance of teacher-parent partnerships is the teachers do teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic

involvement among low-income families, considering the major theme as strategies that teachers use to engage low-income families in their child's academic progress. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families, considering the major theme as challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families, challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families strategies that teachers use to engage low-income families in their child's academic progress. I analyzed the narration of challenges in challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families. Based on the research questions that the study dealt with, the reflection can be adapted to directly address those questions. Here's a response that specifically focuses on how teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families while emphasizing the importance of teacher-parent partnerships is the teachers do teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families, considering the major theme as strategies that teachers use to engage low-income families in their child's academic progress, and the importance of effective communication. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families, considering the major theme as challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families, I analyzed the narration of challenges in challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families. Based on the research questions that the study dealt with, the reflection can be adapted to directly address those questions. I analyzed the narration of challenges in challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families. Based on the research questions that the study dealt with, the reflection can be adapted to directly address those questions. Here's a

response that specifically focuses on how teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families while emphasizing the importance of teacher-parent partnerships is the teachers do teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families, considering the major theme as strategies that teachers use to engage low-income families in their child's academic progress, and the importance of effective communication. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families, considering the major theme as challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families, strategies that teachers use to engage low-income families in their child's academic progress, and the importance of effective communication.

3.2.2. Strategies that teachers use to engage low-income families in their child's academic progress—On the other hand, teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families, considering the major third theme as the Strategies that teachers use to engage low-income families in their child's academic progress. Moreover, a response that specifically focuses on how teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families while emphasizing the importance of teacher-parent partnerships is the teachers do teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families, considering the theme as strategies that teachers used to engage low-income families in their child's academic progress, and the importance of effective communication strategies that teachers use to engage low-income families in their child's academic progress. I analyzed the narration of challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families. Based on the research questions that the study dealt with, the reflection can be adapted to directly

address those questions. Based on the interview data gathered from the teachers coping with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families, considering the major theme as challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families, strategies that teachers use to engage low-income families in the importance of effective communication. Here's a response that specifically focuses on how teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families while emphasizing the importance of teacher-parent partnerships is the teachers do teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families, considering the major theme as strategies that teachers use to engage low-income families in their child's academic progress, and the importance of effective communication. This approach enables us to cope with these challenges effectively, fosters open lines of communication, and ultimately creates a more inclusive and supportive educational environment for our students. It's a fundamental part of our responsibility as educators, and I believe it's a path that benefits not only the families but also the entire educational community. I analyzed the narration in practical terms, to cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families, teachers must take proactive steps. We must tailor our approach to the specific needs of each family, provide additional resources where necessary, and create flexible solutions that accommodate demanding work schedules and other constraints. I analyzed the narration highlights the importance of teacher-parent partnerships to cope with the challenges faced by low-income families in their academic involvement. By actively fostering these partnerships, we, as teachers, can overcome barriers, enhance parental engagement, and create an inclusive and supportive educational environment for all our students. It's a fundamental part of our role and a powerful tool for addressing the

issues at the heart of our research questions.

3.2.3. *Importance of effective communication*—On the other hand, to cope with the challenges, teachers must be proactive in tailoring our approach to meet the specific needs of each family. We can provide additional resources, adapt our communication methods, and be flexible in accommodating parent-teacher meetings. All these efforts help in addressing the importance of effective communication. I analyzed the narration highlights that to cope with the challenges, teachers must be proactive in tailoring their approach to meet the specific needs of each family. We can provide additional resources, adapt our communication methods, and be flexible in accommodating parent-teacher meetings. All these efforts help in addressing the importance of effective communication. Based on this statement, I analyzed the narration on the other hand, these responses from educational outcomes of effective teacher-parent partnerships. By actively fostering these partnerships, we, as teachers, can overcome barriers, enhance parental engagement, and create an inclusive and supportive educational environment for all our students. It's a fundamental part of our role and a powerful tool for addressing the issues at the heart of our research questions. Reyes and Galang (2019) also maintained that parents and family contribute positively to students' motivation in school. An extensive search of the literature, as well as direct communication with several prominent Filipino scholars in the Philippines and other Southeast Asian countries, resulted in finding only one published empirical study focusing on academic involvement among Filipinos, findings revealed that middle- and high-income Filipino parents scored high in involvement with homework and in volunteering (Blair, 2019). I analyzed the narration highlights the importance of teacher-parent partnerships to cope with the challenges faced by low-income families in their academic involvement. By actively

Fig. 4. How Teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families

fostering these partnerships, teachers, can overcome barriers, enhance parental engagement, and create an inclusive and supportive educational environment for all our students. It's a fundamental part of our role and a powerful tool for addressing the issues at the heart of our research questions. I analyzed the narration for teachers, our research highlights the integral role of teacher-parent partnerships in helping low-income families overcome the barriers to academic involvement. This approach enables us to cope with these challenges effectively, fosters open lines of communication, and ultimately creates a more inclusive and supportive educational environment for our students. It's a fundamental part of our responsibility as educators, and I believe it's a path that benefits not only the families but also the entire educational community. According to the 2018 Annual Poverty Indicators Survey conducted by the National Statistics Office, lack of personal interest in school, and the high cost of education are the top two reasons why Filipino youth do

not attend school. Despite government efforts to improve the access and state of education in the country, such as participating in the United Nations' Millennium Development Goal and allocating the biggest portion of the national budget to the Department of Education youth (FLEMMS, 2018). Moreover, teacher-parent partnerships serve as a coping mechanism for us as educators, too. When we see the positive outcomes of these partnerships, it not only boosts our morale but also reaffirms our commitment to our students' success. It's a rewarding experience to witness how these relationships can break down barriers and enhance the educational experience for all involved. However, many educators believe that the country is not well equipped for this transition to be successful. In fact, the current secretary of the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) commented that many public schools still do not have enough classrooms, teachers, chairs, and books (Ibon Foundation, 2019).

3.3. *Educational management insight are drawn from the study*—The third objective of this study is to narration for teachers, our re-

search highlights the integral role of teacher-parent partnerships in helping low-income families overcome the barriers to academic involve-

ment. This approach enables us to cope with these challenges effectively, fosters open lines of communication, and ultimately creates a more inclusive and supportive educational environment for our students. The study would specifically seek to answer the queries, of what educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study findings of the study having emerged major themes such as educational outcomes of effective teacher-parent partnerships, incorporating the perspectives and input of low-income families, and policies and practices to promote educational equity for low-income families.

3.3.1. Educational outcomes of effective teacher-parent partnerships—Based on the interview data gathered highlights the integral role of teacher-parent partnerships in helping low-income families overcome the barriers to academic involvement. This approach enables us to cope with these challenges effectively, fosters open lines of communication, and ultimately creates a more inclusive and supportive educational environment for our students addressing the educational outcomes of effective teacher-parent partnerships. As I analyzed the narration of the study would specifically seek to answer the queries, of what educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study findings of the study having emerged major themes such as educational outcomes of effective teacher-parent partnerships, incorporating the perspectives and input of low-income families educational outcomes of effective teacher-parent partnerships. As I analyzed the narration of the study would specifically seek to answer the queries, of what educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study findings of the study having emerged major themes such as educational outcomes of effective teacher-parent partnerships, incorporating the perspectives and input of low-income families educational outcomes of effective teacher-parent partnerships. As I analyzed the narration of the study would

specifically seek to answer the queries, teachers that may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to teacher-parent partnership of what educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study findings of the study having emerged major theme incorporating the perspectives and input of low-income families, and policies and practices to promote educational equity for low-income families

3.3.2. Incorporating the perspectives and input of low-income families—On the other hand, teachers may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to the teacher-parent partnership of what educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study findings of the study having emerged as major theme incorporating the perspectives and input of low-income families. As I analyzed the narration, teachers may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to teacher-parent partnership of what educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study findings of the study having emerged major theme policies and practices to promote educational equity for low-income families. As I analyzed the narration, teachers may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to the teacher-parent partnership of what educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study findings of the study having emerged major theme policies and practices to promote educational equity for low-income families. As I analyzed the narration, teachers may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to the teacher-parent partnership of what educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study findings of the study having emerged major theme policies and practices to promote educational equity for low-income families. As I analyzed the narration, teachers may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to the teacher-parent partnership of what educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study findings of the study having emerged major theme policies and practices to promote educational equity for low-income families. As I analyzed the narration, teachers may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to the teacher-parent partnership of what educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study findings of the study having emerged

major theme policies and practices to promote educational equity for low-income families.

3.3.3. Policies and practices to promote educational equity for low-income families—As I analyzed the narration explored the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning shifting to student-centered learning often requires a reevaluation of grading and assessment methods. Teachers need to find alternative ways to assess student progress without solely relying on traditional exams, which can be time-consuming. Navigating parental expectations rooted in their own traditional educational experiences can be a real challenge. Convincing parents of the advantages of student-centered learning while addressing their concerns is an ongoing effort. Collaboration and peer learning, explore the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward student-centered learning. Some students adapt seamlessly while others may struggle with the shift they explored the perceptions and practices of junior high school teachers toward Collaboration and peer learning Based on this statement, I analyzed the narration of others having strong administrative support is crucial for the successful implementation of student-centered practices. A lack of support from school administrators can hinder efforts to balance traditions with innovative methods, traditions with student-centered learning can be time intensive. Finding the It's evident from our research that teachers do indeed encounter numerous challenges when it comes to engaging low-income families in the academic journey of their children. These challenges can be multifaceted, including financial constraints, time limitations, language barriers, and the absence of educational resources at home. Coping with these hurdles requires a thoughtful and strategic approach. Teacher-parent partnerships have emerged as a powerful coping mechanism. Our study underscores the significance of these partnerships in breaking down barriers. By ac-

tively fostering connections with parents, teachers can build bridges between the school and home, making education a more inclusive and collaborative process. This approach is not only effective but also aligns with our responsibility as educators to create a supportive environment for all our students, regardless of their economic background. One striking observation from our research is that low-income families often have a strong desire to be involved in their child's education. They recognize its importance and are willing to participate, but their circumstances make it challenging. This reinforces the importance of teacher-parent partnerships, which can provide the necessary support and guidance to help these families engage more effectively. Moreover, teacher-parent partnerships serve as a coping mechanism for us as educators, too. When we see the positive outcomes of these partnerships, it not only boosts our morale but also reaffirms our commitment to our students' success. It's a rewarding experience to witness how these relationships can break down barriers and enhance the educational experience for all involved. In practical terms, to cope with the challenges, teachers must be proactive in tailoring our approach to meet the specific needs of each family. We can provide additional resources, adapt our communication methods, and be flexible in accommodating parent-teacher meetings. All these efforts help in addressing the multifaceted challenges low-income families face. As I analyzed the In research highlights the integral role of teacher-parent partnerships in helping low-income families overcome the barriers to academic involvement. This approach enables us to cope with these challenges effectively, fosters open lines of communication, and ultimately creates a more inclusive and supportive educational environment for our students. It's a fundamental part of our responsibility as educators, and I believe it's a path that benefits not only the families but also the entire educational community. As I analyzed the

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Study

narration of A notable challenge is the significant variation in student readiness for student-centered learning. Some students embrace the shift with ease, while others struggle to adapt. This necessitates a flexible teaching approach. How can curriculum design and implementation support student-centered learning practices, and what are the challenges and opportunities of this approach? A study by Escobar-Cedano et al. (2021) found that a competency-based curriculum design supported the implementation

of student-centered learning practices. How can parents and community members be involved in supporting student-centered learning practices, and what are the benefits and challenges of this approach? A study by Gao et al. (2021) found that parent and community involvement can support student-centered learning practices, but that communication and collaboration must be established to ensure a shared understanding of these practices.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on its findings. Future directions in culturally responsive teachers through the lens of classroom advisers are also discussed here. The target participants for this study were twelve (12) elementary faculty members who were still teaching during the first semester of the school year 2022-2023. This study utilized an in-depth interview. The researcher considered the faculty from selected public schools who are still teaching. From this population, a sample of twelve (12) elementary school teachers who are still teaching during the school year 2022-2023 was purposefully selected. The respondents will join for an in-depth interview (IDI). The study was to explore the following research questions: What is the lived experience of teachers that may highlight their perspective of low-income families related to teacher-parent partnership? How do teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families? What educational insights can be derived from the study findings? Teachers' perspective of family low-income learners related to teacher-parent partnership barriers to academic involvement among low-income families building trust and rapport with low-income families' resources and support for teachers working with low-income families. Challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families include strategies teachers use to engage low-income families in their child's academic

progress. The importance of effective communication educational outcomes of effective teacher-parent partnerships incorporating the perspectives and input of low-income families policies and practices to promote educational equity for low-income families.

4.1. Findings—The findings revealed that low-income families encounter various challenges that hinder their academic involvement. The first objective of this study is to examine the lived experience of teachers, which may highlight their perspective of family low incomes related to teacher-parent partnership. The study specifically sought to answer the following queries, having three significant themes: barriers to academic involvement among low-income families, building trust and rapport with low-income families, and lastly, resources and support for teachers working with low-income families. The second objective of this study is to determine whether teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families. The three major themes are Challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families, Strategies that teachers use to engage low-income families in their children's academic progress, and the importance of effective communication. The third objective of this study was to narration for teachers, our research highlights the integral role of teacher-parent partnerships in helping low-income families overcome the barriers to academic involvement. This approach enables us to cope with these challenges effectively, fosters open lines of communication, and ultimately creates a more inclusive and supportive educational environment for our students.

4.1.1. Implications—The research highlighted, based on the interview data gathered from the teachers' perspective of family low-income learners related to teacher-parent partnership, emerged with the theme of barriers to academic involvement among low-income families, building trust and rapport with low-income families, resources, and support for teachers working with low-income families. Based on

the interview data gathered from the teachers, do teachers cope with the challenges that hinder academic involvement among low-income families? Consider the three major themes as challenges faced by teachers who work with low-income families: Strategies that teachers use to engage low-income families in their child's academic progress and the importance of effective communication. The study would specifically seek to answer the queries of what educational insight and practices can be drawn from the study findings, which have emerged major themes such as educational outcomes of effective teacher-parent partnerships, incorporating the perspectives and input of low-income families, and policies and practices to promote educational equity for low-income families. Despite these challenges, the research revealed that low-income families strongly desire to be involved in their child's education. They recognize the importance of education and express a willingness to participate actively.

4.2. Future Directions—The school head may help to estimate the importance of this study to help the teachers and parents to give a background on how to handle issues similar to this. The study showed that teachers often grapple with the emotional aspects of their role when trying to engage low-income families. They expressed frustration and a sense of helplessness when they witnessed parents' struggles and their inability to participate fully in their child's education. The research emphasized that teacher-parent partnerships play a significant role in helping low-income families overcome the barriers to academic involvement. When teachers actively establish connections with parents, it fosters open lines of communication and creates an inclusive environment. In the future, we should explore and

implement more flexible assessment models that align with student-centered practices. This may require a shift away from traditional exams and a focus on alternative ways of evaluating student progress. Effective communication and empathy emerged as crucial elements in teacher-parent partnerships. Teachers who actively listen to parents' concerns, understand their unique situations, and offer support successfully overcome the barriers. The teachers. Future directions may encourage mentorship and collaboration among teachers. Experienced teachers could guide those who were new to student-centered practices, creating a supportive environment for growth and development. To address challenges, future directions should involve customized teacher training programs. Not all teachers face the same obstacles, and personalized training can help them overcome their specific challenges. The study found that collaborative problem-solving between teachers and parents, focusing on the particular needs of each family, was instrumental in addressing financial constraints, time limitations, and other challenges faced by low-income families. Parents and stakeholders. These findings illustrate the challenges low-income families face in engaging in their children's education and the critical role that teachers play in coping with these challenges. Teacher-parent partnerships emerged as a powerful strategy, facilitating open communication, empathy, resource support, and collaborative problem-solving. By actively engaging with low-income families and addressing their specific needs, teachers could help break down the barriers to academic involvement, ultimately benefitting their students.

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